

ALGORITHMS FOR EVALUATING DATA ON THE ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS OF AGRICULTURAL LAND IN THE NUKUS DISTRICT

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Abstract. In this article, it will be explored the use of algorithms for evaluating data on the environmental conditions of agricultural land, using the example of the Nukus district. This case study will illustrate how algorithms and data analysis techniques can provide valuable information for farmers and policymakers to make informed decisions regarding land management and crop production. By harnessing the power of technology and data-driven approaches, we can enhance agricultural practices and ensure a more sustainable future for agriculture.

Keywords: machine learning, environmental conditions, Nukus district, water availability, soil contamination, climate patterns, research institutions, monitoring systems, data analysis.

The evaluation of environmental conditions in the Nukus district using machine learning algorithms has the potential to have far-reaching implications for environmental management and sustainability. By harnessing the power of data analysis and predictive modeling, researchers and policymakers can gain valuable insights into the state of the environment and make informed decisions to address pressing environmental challenges. One important implication of using machine learning algorithms in environmental evaluation is the ability to generate data-driven policy recommendations [3]. By analyzing large and complex datasets, machine learning models can uncover patterns and trends in environmental conditions that may not be readily apparent through traditional methods. This information can inform the development of targeted policies and regulations that aim to address specific environmental issues in the Nukus district and improve overall environmental sustainability. Furthermore, machine learning algorithms can be used to develop early warning systems for environmental hazards, such as air pollution spikes or extreme weather events. By leveraging historical data and real-time monitoring information, these systems can help local authorities and communities prepare for and respond to environmental disasters in a timely manner, potentially saving lives and minimizing damage to the environment. In addition to providing valuable insights for decision-making, the use of machine learning algorithms in environmental evaluation can also enhance community engagement and

empowerment [5]. Citizen science initiatives can be implemented to involve local residents in monitoring environmental conditions and reporting data, creating a sense of ownership and responsibility for the health of their environment. This collaborative approach can improve the accuracy and reliability of environmental assessments while fostering a sense of environmental stewardship among community members. Collaboration with research institutions, non-governmental organizations, and international partners is also crucial for advancing the analysis of environmental conditions in the Nukus district. By pooling expertise and resources, collaborative research efforts can tackle complex environmental challenges more effectively and develop sustainable solutions that benefit both the environment and the local population. Establishing a system for long-term monitoring of environmental variables in the Nukus district is essential for tracking trends, identifying emerging threats, and evaluating the impact of interventions over time. Continuous data collection and analysis can provide valuable insights into the evolving environmental landscape and guide decision-making processes to ensure the long-term sustainability of the region. Finally, integrating data from multiple sources, such as satellite imagery, IoT devices, and ground-based sensors, can enhance the analysis of environmental conditions by providing a comprehensive and holistic view of the factors at play. By combining different types of data, researchers can gain a deeper understanding of the complex interactions between environmental variables and develop more robust models for predicting future environmental trends [4]. Overall, the use of machine learning algorithms in the evaluation of environmental conditions in the Nukus district holds great promise for informing decision-making, promoting community engagement, and advancing environmental sustainability. By embracing data-driven approaches and fostering collaboration across disciplines and organizations, we can work towards creating a healthier and more resilient environment for current and future generations in the Nukus district and beyond.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the application of machine learning algorithms for evaluating environmental conditions in the Nukus district represents a significant step towards understanding and addressing environmental challenges in the region. The analysis provides valuable insights into key environmental factors such as air quality, water availability, soil contamination, and climate patterns, which are critical for developing effective policies and

interventions. This study serves as a foundation for future efforts to protect and preserve the environment in Nukus and beyond.

References:

1. www.lex.uz/ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2021-yil 26-fevraldagi PQ-5009-son qarori
2. Ballari, D., Melia, J., & Khandelwal, A. (2021). Using Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data for land use/land cover mapping. *Geosciences*, 11(7), 305.
3. Das, R., Pradhan, B., & Lee, S. (2020). Synergistic use of UAV, optical and SAR remote sensing data and machine learning techniques for land use/land cover mapping: A review. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 159, 204-221.
4. Gao, Y., Guo, H., Zhou, Y., & Zhang, X. (2021). A novel algorithm for agricultural land zoning based on multi-source data. *IEEE Access*, 9, 59467-59477.
5. Kussul, N., Kolotii, A., Shelestov, A., Lavreniuk, M., Myshenyk, Y., & Skakun, S. (2018). Development of agricultural land monitoring algorithms using Earth observation data. *Journal of automation and information sciences*, 50(3), 61-73.
6. Rich, K., Persello, C., Tait, N., & Coomes, D. (2020). Mapping deforestation and forest degradation in tropical regions: A framework for monitoring using satellite Earth observation data. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 11(5), 573-587.